

Hi [interviewee's name], thank you for taking the time to speak with me today and participate in this study. My name is [interviewer's name].

The purpose of our discussion is to have your insights, perspectives, and feedback on our findings. This interview will take around 1 hour. I am sending you a link to the document with our findings. [Summary document link]

[Briefing about the study and goals] Each page has detailed findings, first I will walk you through it and then we will have a discussion. Let me know when you are on the document.

I'll be reading from a script to be consistent. Also, I would like to audio record this interview with your permission, to ensure I accurately capture our conversation. The recording will only be used for analysis related to this study and all identifiable data will be kept confidential. Is it okay to record?

Alright, let's start on page 1:

[Finding 1 phases - L1, L2, I1, I2]

Here are the phases participants identified involved with SE learning and implementation:

[Brief on each phase]

- Learning (Initial - L1) learning SE concepts from scratch without prior knowledge.
- Learning (Incremental - L2) learning after having some background knowledge / refining understanding.
- Implementation (Initial - I1) initial stages of software implementations (e.g. setting up frameworks, boilerplates, templates, etc)
- Implementation (Advanced - I2) contributing to existing code bases or their own term/capstone projects.

1. Considering your SE course structure(s), could you identify which parts of your courseware and course assignments correspond to each of the four phases?

Now, onto the next finding on page 2:

The students reported that they perceived benefits in using genAI only for incremental learning and initial implementations while they perceived only challenges in initial learning and advanced implementations.

Fig.1 highlights each of the phases and the challenges/benefits perceived by students in each one of them.

[Walk through the figure with examples]

Please take a detailed look at the figure, once you are done we will proceed with the discussion with the figure.

[Wait till they are done]

Now, let's walk through each of the phases.

1. Reflecting on your observations and experiences with students in the course,

- **Which of the reported benefits or challenges have you noticed that students encounter?**
 - **Can you give some examples or situations?**
-

Alright, now let's move on to the next finding

We identified the causes and consequences of the challenges faced by students (Fig 2). We will focus our discussion on the links between the challenges students report and the impacts of those challenges.

[Walk through Figure 2]

[Briefing]

As you saw in the previous finding, the challenges are grouped into 5 categories:

C1: Unclear understanding of genAI and its use

C2: Difficulty in effectively communicating needs or context

C3: Difficulty in aligning genAI to process or preferences

C4: Issues in obtaining proper rationales behind genAI responses

C5: Difficulty in appropriately using genAI responses

These challenges negatively impacted learning, tasks, self-perception, and genAI adoption for students. Specifically,

1. C2, C3, C4, C5 -> Impact on learning (incomplete understanding of concepts, learning wrong)
2. C1, C2, C3, C4, C5 -> Impact on task (figuring things out on their own, slowed them down, abandonment of tasks)
3. C1, C2, C5 -> Impact on self (over-reliance, self-doubt, and frustration)
4. C1, C2, C4, C5 -> Impact on genAI adoption (distrust, steered away from using genAI)

Please take a detailed look at the figure, once you are done we will proceed with the discussion with the figure.

[Wait till they are done]

1. Which of these did you find relevant to your experience with students? Which aspects were known, versus which are not?

- **Could you walk us through this?**

2. Reflecting on the challenges (C1 to C5) and their impacts, what measures need to be currently addressed?

Alright, at the end, any thoughts or insights you want to add or share about your experiences and/or the findings?